

The Influence of Administrative Supervision on Teacher's Instructional Performance and Students' Academic Achievement

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Abstract: This study determined the influence of administrative supervision on teachers' instructional performance and students' academic achievement at Julio Ledesma National High School. Specifically, it examined supervision practices in terms of classroom observation, mentoring, coaching, and feedback, and their relationship with teaching performance and learner outcomes. A descriptive correlational research design was employed. Data were gathered from teachers handling Grades 9, 10, and 12 of Julio Ledesma National High School, San Carlos City, using validated survey questionnaires, while students' academic achievement was obtained from school academic records. Statistical tools such as weighted mean and Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficient were used to analyze the data. The results revealed that administrative supervision was highly practiced and development-oriented. Teachers' instructional performance was rated as high, whereas students' academic achievement was generally satisfactory. A strong and significant relationship was found between administrative supervision and teachers' instructional performance, indicating that effective supervision enhances teaching effectiveness. However, no significant direct relationship was established between administrative supervision and students' academic achievement, suggesting an indirect influence through improved instructional performance. The study concludes that administrative supervision is essential for strengthening instructional quality and recommends the continued implementation of development-focused supervisory practices to support effective teaching and improved learning outcomes.

Keywords: Administrative supervision; instructional performance; academic achievement; instructional leadership, descriptive-correlation design secondary education of Julio Ledesma National High School, San Carlos City.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Background of Study

Administrative supervision involves purposeful activities such as classroom observations, teacher evaluations, mentoring, coaching, and feedback sessions. Its primary aim is to support teachers' professional growth and ensure that instructional delivery meets established standards. According to Martinez (2024) her findings highlighted the importance of school administrators preparing and observing well to improve both the caliber of instruction and the learning outcomes of their students. When implemented effectively, supervision does not merely assess but empowers teachers, helping them refine their teaching strategies, align instruction with learning goals, and adapt to students' needs (Waqas et al., 2023).

Globally, numerous studies have demonstrated the link between academic supervision and improved teacher performance and student outcomes. For instance, a meta-analysis by Park et al. (2024) concluded that leadership for learning including supervision significantly improves teacher

instructional quality, which in turn enhances student academic achievement. In Uganda, Abuko and Andala (2023) found that strong instructional supervision had a highly positive correlation with teacher performance ($r = .8421$), while in Indonesia, Dewi et al. (2023) confirmed that principal supervision and leadership style were key predictors of student academic success.

From a regional perspective, Bangladesh believed that to achieve both qualitative and quantitative instructional delivery, the supervisory roles of the AUEOs should improve educational programs that would aid teachers. It could easily be deduced that supervision is an indispensable variable in the teaching-learning process as well as the overall school and educational objectives (Alam et al 2021). In relation to this, supervisors should encourage the teachers to participate in various training, study assignments formally, workshops either through independent study or through professional learning communities to help them developed and enhanced their teaching practices

In the Philippine context, instructional leadership is one of the skills that must be possessed by a school principal and is one of the most important components in DepEd schools (Anabo 2024). Similarly, Andoy (2023) noted a positive relationship between school heads' supervisory skills and both teacher performance and student achievement in selected Grade 8 learners. Based on the study of School Heads' Instructional Supervisory Skills and Teachers' Performance which was conducted in Bacolod City, Negros Occidental by Anjel Dane G. Go (2024) instructional supervision is one of the processes by which school administrators tried to attain viable standards of academic performance and output. The goal of supervision is to improve the quality of instructions, as it has a direct responsibility of the teachers, the need to develop the Standards, Processes, and Tools for Instructional Supervision, which will enhance the guidance and support essential to develop teacher instructional competence.

These dynamics are particularly relevant at the Julio Ledesma National High School. Like many other public schools in the country, the school faces ongoing challenges in sustaining high levels of academic achievement and maintaining consistent instructional performance.

Given these realities, the purpose of this study is to investigate the influence of administrative supervision on teachers' instructional performance and students' academic achievement at Julio Ledesma National High School, as there is little to no established research conducted in this institution regarding the matter. This study aims to fill this research gap.

The findings will provide essential insights for school administrators, policymakers, and educators to improve instructional leadership strategies that are development-oriented, data-driven, and impactful on both teacher practice and student outcomes.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Literature

On The Level of influence in Administrative Supervision

The level of influence of administrative supervision is a critical determinant of organizational success and institutional performance. Effective administrative supervision ensures that institutional goals are efficiently achieved through proper planning, coordination, monitoring, and evaluation of staff performance and resources (Eviyanti, Miftahudin, Supardi, & Gunawan, 2025). When supervision is carried out effectively, it enhances accountability, transparency, and the quality of decision-making within the organization, thereby fostering a culture of continuous improvement (Liu & Wang, 2025).

In educational settings, the effectiveness of supervision directly influences teachers' professional growth and the quality of instruction. Studies have revealed that when administrators demonstrate high supervisory competence through feedback, mentoring, and evaluation, teachers' self-efficacy, motivation, and instructional performance improve significantly (Esllera & Escala, 2024; Siahaan, 2024). Consequently, this contributes to overall institutional effectiveness and improved learner outcomes.

Moreover, effective administrative supervision promotes a positive organizational culture by aligning administrative practices with shared goals and collaborative values (Macalisang, 2023). Conversely, poor or ineffective supervision often leads to mismanagement, low staff morale and diminished productivity (Coronel, 2024). Therefore, evaluating and enhancing the level of effectiveness in administrative supervision is not only essential for individual professional development but also for ensuring institutional sustainability and excellence (Sanchez, Labordo, & Martir, 2024).

On the Level of Teachers' Instructional Performance

Teachers' instructional performance is a crucial factor that determines the quality of academic outcomes and the overall impact of the academic system. High instructional performance reflects teachers' ability to plan, implement, and evaluate learning activities that promote meaningful student engagement and achievement (Lara, Wardiah, & Suherman, 2025). Teachers who consistently demonstrate strong instructional competence create positive learning environments, apply varied teaching strategies, and effectively assess student progress, all of which contribute to academic excellence (Coronel, 2024).

Several studies have shown that teachers' instructional performance is influenced by multiple factors, such as supervisory support, professional development, motivation, and leadership practices of school heads (Siahaan, 2024; Esllera & Escala, 2024).

Effective supervision and administrative guidance enhance teachers' pedagogical skills and confidence, resulting in improved instructional delivery and learner outcomes (Ayu, 2024). Conversely, low levels of instructional performance often arise from inadequate supervision, lack of resources, and limited professional development opportunities, which hinder the achievement of educational goals (Eviyanti, Miftahudin, Supardi, & Gunawan, 2025).

Therefore, assessing and continuously improving the level of teachers' instructional performance is vital to ensure that educational institutions maintain high standards of teaching and learning effectiveness (Sanchez, Labordo, & Martir, 2024).

The Level of Students' Academic Achievement

The level of students' academic achievement is a vital metric for gauging educational effectiveness and student learning outcomes. It encompasses students' attainment of knowledge, skills, and competencies aligned with curricular goals and reflects both individual efforts and systemic support (Kaya & Erdem, 2021).

Research indicates that factors such as students' confidence in learning abilities and economic and social status are among the most influential contributing factors of achievement levels, underscoring the interplay of student attitudes and contextual resources (Sánchez-Caballero et al., 2021; see School of Education meta-analysis). Another study has shown that students who demonstrate strong self-management and academic self-efficacy consistently achieve higher academic performance, as they are more capable of regulating their learning behaviors, setting achievable goals, and maintaining motivation despite challenges (Zhou, 2022).

Moreover, academic achievement embodies the collective outcome of effective teaching, supportive school environments, and positive student attitudes, serving as an essential benchmark for assessing learning success and guiding educational policy reform (Nguyen & Tran, 2024).

Foreign Literature

Administrative supervision is a crucial factor in improving both teachers' instructional outcomes and learners' academic achievements. By providing systematic classroom observation, constructive feedback, mentoring, and professional development, school leaders support teachers in improving their lesson planning, instructional strategies, and classroom management (Muttaqin et al., 2023). When school leaders provide consistent guidance through classroom observations, constructive feedback, mentoring, and professional development, teachers become more confident and skilled in delivering lessons and managing classrooms (Muttaqin et al., 2023; Marlina, Su'ad, & Sukirman,

2022). This supportive supervision not only improves teaching practices but also has a clear impact on students' learning outcomes, as well-supervised teachers are better equipped to engage students and meet their diverse needs (Febrina et al., 2025; Novita Sari, 2025).

Moreover, research shows that teacher performance serves as a bridge between leadership practices and student achievement, meaning that effective supervision indirectly boosts student success by enhancing teachers' abilities (MDPI, 2024). In essence, investing in strong and thoughtful administrative supervision creates a positive ripple effect which is better-supported teachers leading to more engaged students and higher academic achievement. Such support not only strengthens teachers' competence and confidence but also encourages the adoption of more effective teaching practices, which directly influence student learning outcomes (Al Faruq, Sunoko, Rozi, & Salim, 2024).

Research abroad shows that instructional supervision is a key driver of teacher growth and improved classroom practice. In a recent study, He, Guo, and Abazie (2024) found that when school leaders actively engage in instructional leadership through regular monitoring, feedback, and professional development, teachers demonstrate stronger professional competence and greater confidence in delivering instruction.

Local Studies

In the Philippine educational context, mounting local evidence highlights the importance of administrative and instructional supervision in enhancing teachers' instructional performance and, by extension, supporting students' academic achievement. For instance, Sanchez and Lugo (2023) found that in Region XI, instructional supervision and ICT integration were significantly correlated with teacher proficiency in public elementary schools. Castillo (2024) discovered in Hinabangan, Samar District 1 a "very high" positive correlation between school-heads' instructional supervision strategies and teachers' instructional performance.

Quilala and Tantiado (2025) reported among 166 teachers in Cagayan de Oro City a positive relationship between instructional supervision and teacher efficacy, though modest in strength. San Roque and Valle (2025) demonstrated that in Cagayan de Oro elementary schools, school heads' instructional supervision had a significant impact on teachers' self-efficacy.

Moreover, Concepcion and Labitad (2025) examined master teachers' instructional supervisory skills in Bukidnon and found these to be positively and significantly linked to teachers' teaching performance. Daigon and Alcopra (2024) likewise showed that teachers in Impasugong I District (Bukidnon) perceived high levels of instructional supervision practices and that these were significantly associated with teacher efficacy. Obuta, Salva & Ferenal (2023) in Valencia City found that school heads' instructional supervisory skills were meaningfully related to teacher performance, as measured by IPCRF ratings. Duras (2024) in Eastern Samar concluded that while instructional supervision practices and professional learning communities were perceived as "highly practiced," only some schools had reached mastery in School-Based Management quality parameters.

In similar cases, Reyes and Oropa (2025) focused on master teachers in Surigao del Sur and found that although instructional supervision was highly manifested, no statistically significant direct link was found between teacher performance and learner academic performance. Finally, Saro, Pelesco, Abiao, Longaquit and Palanog (2025) explored the extent of teachers' manifestation toward instructional supervision and technical assistance in Agusan del Sur and found a positive association with student academic success. Together, these studies indicate that when school administrators and master teachers engage in consistent, supportive, and structured supervisory practices such as classroom observations, mentoring, post-observation feedback, and professional development teachers are more likely to exhibit higher instructional performance, which sets more favorable conditions for student learning outcomes. However, the chain from supervision to teacher performance to student achievement remains unevenly evidenced in the Philippine setting.

In the context of the Negros Island Region, local research also supports the growing evidence that administrative and instructional supervision plays a vital role in improving teachers' instructional performance and, ultimately, student achievement. Comighud, Futralan, and Cordevilla (2024) conducted a study in the Division of Bayawan City, Negros Oriental, and found that teachers perceived instructional supervision to be "very high" across dimensions such as planning, dialogue, and evaluation. Their findings highlighted that effective supervision fosters open communication and professional collaboration between school heads and teachers, which enhances instructional delivery.

Similarly, Antonio and Eslabon (2023) explored the relationship between school heads' instructional supervisory skills and teachers' performance in Bacolod City, Negros Occidental, Philippines. Their study revealed that while school heads possessed a high level of supervisory competence, there was no significant correlation between supervisory skills and teacher performance. This suggests that the impact of supervision may depend on how supervisory practices are implemented and perceived by teachers. Taken together, these Negros-based studies echo national findings such as those of Sanchez and Lugo (2023), Castillo (2024), and Reyes and Oropa (2025), which emphasize the importance of supportive, participatory, and consistent supervision in enhancing teaching quality and sustaining academic growth, even as the direct link to student achievement may vary across local contexts.

This part synthesizes that both foreign and local literature show that administrative supervision plays a central role in strengthening teachers' instructional performance and improving student learning. International studies consistently highlight that when school leaders provide meaningful classroom observation, constructive feedback, mentoring, and professional development, teachers become more confident, better prepared, and more effective in managing their classrooms and delivering lessons.

This supportive environment not only elevates teaching quality but also creates a ripple effect that leads to higher student engagement and academic achievements. Strong supervision enhances teachers' skills, which then becomes the bridge through which leadership practices translate into better student outcomes.

Similarly, local studies in the Philippines from Region XI to Cagayan de Oro, Bukidnon, Samar, Eastern Samar, and Surigao del Sur affirm the importance of consistent and thoughtful instructional supervision. The findings show that when school heads and master teachers engage in clear, collaborative, and structured supervisory practices, teachers demonstrate higher efficacy and improved instructional performance, setting more favorable conditions for student success, even though the direct link to student achievement is not always uniform.

Moreover, research within the Negros Island Region echoes these trends: teachers perceive supervision as highly practiced and beneficial, although its impact depends greatly on how strategies are implemented and received. Overall, the literature illustrates that supportive and well-executed administrative supervision strengthens teaching practices and helps cultivate an environment where students are more engaged, better supported, and more likely to succeed academically.

Furthermore, the literature makes it clear that administrative supervision is most effective when it goes beyond simple monitoring and becomes a genuine source of guidance and support for teachers. When school leaders plan carefully, offer meaningful feedback, mentor teachers, and consistently check on progress, they help create a school environment in which teachers feel valued and empowered to grow (Eviyanti et al., 2025; Liu & Wang, 2025). In many cases, this kind of supportive supervision strengthens teachers' sense of responsibility, boosts their professional confidence, and enhances the quality of their instruction (Esllera & Escala, 2024; Siahaan, 2024).

Overall, the reviewed literature establishes that effective administrative supervision is a foundational component of school success. It enhances teachers' instructional performance through mentoring, monitoring, and professional development, which, in turn, creates learning environments

conducive to improved student achievement. Although the strength of these relationships varies across contexts, supervision consistently emerges as a catalyst for teacher growth and academic performance. These insights align directly with the focus of the present study in Julio Ledesma National High School, which seeks to determine how administrative supervision influences teacher performance and student academic outcomes within its specific educational setting.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored in several educational and management theories that explain how administrative supervision influences teacher performance and, consequently, student academic achievement. These theories serve as the foundation for understanding the mechanisms through which school leadership and supervision practices impact instructional quality and learning outcomes of the school.

Instructional Supervision Theory indicates the role of school leaders in supporting teachers through observation, feedback, coaching, and reflection. According to Glickman et al., (2014), effective supervision is developmental in nature, focusing on the continuous improvement of teaching practices rather than mere evaluation. This theory suggests that when school administrators provide ongoing constructive supervision, it enhances teacher competency, classroom management, and instructional delivery. This theory underpins the study's investigation into how administrative supervision contributes to teachers' professional development and enhances their teaching performance.

Systems theory views school as interconnected systems in which each part (administrators, teachers, students, curriculum, and environment) interacts to achieve shared goals. Changes or improvements in one component, such as administrative supervision can influence other components like teacher performance and student achievement Von Bertalanffy (1968). This theory promotes the idea of a holistic approach to improving schools. Thus, it justifies examining how administrative supervision serves as a systemic input that can affect teacher behavior in the process and would eventually result in student performance (Owens & Valesky, 2015).

Conceptual Framework

Globally, there is an increasing amount of empirical literature that has reported the effect of administrative supervision on teachers' instructional performance and students' academic achievement or instructional supervision of the teachers to achieve the goals of the school as far as education is concerned.

This study aims to determine the influence of administrative supervision on teachers' instructional performance and students' academic achievement in Julio Ledesma National High School. The respondents are the grade 9,10 and 12 teachers when taken as a whole and grouped with respect to their current teaching loads where they handle students from different year levels. Furthermore, the goal of this study is to examine the level of administrative supervision in Julio Ledesma National High School in terms of classroom observations, feedback and observation practices, and instructional support. Moreover, this study also aims to determine the level of teachers' instructional performance in terms of classroom management, teaching strategies, and assessment practices. This study aimed to determine the level of students' academic achievement in terms of academic performance and classroom participation. Additionally, this study aims to determine whether there is a significant difference between supervision and teachers' instructional performance. Finally, this study aims to determine whether there is a significant difference between administrative supervision and academic performance.

The dependent variables are the student's academic performance indicators, such as class participation and quarterly grades.

The intervening variables are the instructional performance indicators, such as classroom management, teaching strategies, and assessment practices.

Administrative supervision, which is the independent variable, creates an environmental factor that interacts with administrative support in terms of classroom observation, feedback, and evolution practices, and instructional support mediates the impact of administrative supervision on teachers’ instructional performance and students’ academic achievement.

The results of the study highlighting the influence of administrative supervision on teachers’ instructional performance and students’ academic achievement can serve as a valuable foundation in shaping an effective and sustainable development plan for both school administrators and faculty members at Julio Ledesma National High School. The following are the key utilization points and their implications for administrative and faculty development planning. Additionally, the findings from this study can significantly inform the strategic direction of an administration and faculty development plan by aligning supervision practices with instructional improvement and student achievement goals. Through targeted training, enhanced leadership capacity, and a culture of collaboration and reflection, Julio Ledesma National High School can create a more collaborative, responsive, and effective learning environment for its students.

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of the Conceptual Framework

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to determine the influence of administrative supervision on grade 9,10 and 12 teachers’ instructional performance and student’s academic achievement in Julio Ledesma National High.

In particular, it aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of influence in administrative supervision in Julio Ledesma National High School in terms of:
 - a. Classroom observations;

- b. Feedback and evaluation practices; and
 - c. Instructional support?
2. What is the level of teachers' instructional performance in terms of:
 - a. Classroom management;
 - b. Teaching strategies; and
 - c. Assessment practices?
 3. What is the level of students' academic achievement?
 4. Is there a significant relationship between the administrative supervision and its effect on teachers' instructional performance?
 5. Is there a significant relationship between the administrative supervision and its effect students' academic achievement?

HYPOTHESES

In this study, the researcher formulated the following hypotheses:

H_A: There is a significant relationship between administrative supervision and teachers' instructional performance

H_o: There is no significant relationship between administrative supervision and students' academic achievement.

Significance of Study

This study benefits the following groups.

School Administrators. The results of this study may help administrators identify effective supervisory practices that support teachers in improving their teaching strategies, classroom management, and overall instructional effectiveness. The findings may also guide school leaders in improving their supervision programs.

Teachers. This study may assist teachers in recognizing areas where additional guidance or professional development is needed. By understanding how administrative supervision affects their instructional performance, teachers may become more confident, motivated, and capable of delivering quality instructions.

Students. Students are expected to benefit indirectly from this study, as improved instructional practices often lead to more engaging lessons, clearer explanations, and enhanced learning experiences.

Julio Ledesma National High School. The findings may help schools strengthen their supervision practices and promote a more supportive, collaborative, and productive learning environment that benefits both teachers and students.

Future Researchers. This study may serve as a valuable basis for future researchers who intend to conduct related studies on administrative supervision, school leadership, teachers' performance, and student academic outcomes.

Scope of the Study

This study focuses on examining the influence of administrative supervision on teachers' instructional performance and students' academic achievement in Julio Ledesma National High School. Specifically, the study covers teachers handling Grades 9, 10, and 12, as these year levels continue to implement the old curriculum in the current school year. This study investigates how supervisory practices such as classroom observations, feedback, coaching, and professional guidance affect the teaching effectiveness of instructors assigned to these grade levels.

In addition, this study investigated the academic achievement of students taught by these teachers, considering indicators such as academic performance and class participation. The research is limited to the said grade levels and does not include Grade 7, Grade 8, or Grade 11 teachers and students, as these groups are already transitioning to the revised curriculum.

The study was confined to Julio Ledesma National High School and did not extend to other schools within the district or division. The data gathered will reflect the conditions, practices, and experiences within the school during the time of the study.

Definition of Terms

For clarity and consistency, the terms used in this study are defined according to the following operational meaning as applied in this research.

Administrative Supervision: Refers to the activities carried out by school leaders, such as classroom observations, providing feedback, mentoring, and supporting teachers to improve their instructional skills and teaching methods.

Classroom Management: Refers to the strategies and practices employed by the teachers to maintain an organized, orderly, and positive learning environment

Classroom Observation: Refers to the process by which school administrators formally or informally observe classroom instruction to assess teaching practices and provide professional support.

Evaluation Practices: Refer to the procedures and methods used by school administrators to assess and review teachers' instructional performance

Instructional Performance: The ability of teachers to effectively plan, deliver, and manage lessons that engage students and promote learning, including the use of appropriate teaching strategies and classroom management techniques.

Instructional Support: Refers to the assistance, guidance, and resources provided by school administrators to help teachers enhance their teaching effectiveness.

Old Curriculum: The previous educational curriculum followed by Grades 9, 10, and 12 in Julio Ledesma National High School, as opposed to the revised or new curriculum being implemented in other grades.

Students' Academic Achievement: The measurable performance of students in their academic work, often assessed through grades, test scores, class participation, and overall mastery of the curriculum.

CHAPTER 2

METHODOLOGY

This chapter discussed the methodological factors to be observed during the process, research design, respondents, research instruments, reliability and validity, data gathering procedures, data analysis, statistical treatment, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study utilized the quantitative research design, particularly a descriptive-comparative and correlational approach (Creswell, 2013). The statistical design measures the variables to answer the statement of the problems and the hypotheses. Specifically, the descriptive approach shall assess the level of influence of administrative supervision on the grade 9,10 and 12 teacher's instructional performance and the level of students' academic achievement in Julio Ledesma National High School. The total numeration was applied to identify the number of respondents. The correlational approach investigates the significant relationship between the level of effectiveness of administrative supervision and its effect on students' academic achievement.

Respondents

Table 1

Respondents	Frequency (f)	Percentage %
Grade 9	36	36.36 %
Grade 10	22	22.22%
Grade 12	41	41.41 %
Total	99	100 %

The distribution of respondents of the study will be all Grade 9,10 and 12 teachers, which has a total of 99, all 36 Grade 9 teachers, 22 Grade 10 teachers, and 41 Grade 12 teachers, both senior high school and junior high school Plantilla of Julio Ledesma National High School in San Carlos City.

Research Instrument.

Arbitrary Table 2A Administrative Supervision

Scale	Mean Score	Interpretation	Description
5	4.21 - 5.00	Strongly Agree	Consistently exceeds expectations; practices are highly beneficial and well-executed.
4	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	Often meets expectations; practices are generally helpful and properly implemented.
3	2.61 - 3.40	Uncertain	Sometimes it meets expectations; practices are adequate but could be improved.
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Rarely meet expectations; practices lack consistency or impact.
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Does not meet expectations; practices are ineffective or largely absent.

Arbitrary Table 2B Teachers’ Instructional Performance

Scale	Mean Range	Interpretation	Description
5	4.21 - 5.00	Strongly Agree	Performance consistently exceeds standards; exemplary and highly effective practices.
4	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	Performance often meets or slightly exceeds standards; effective and consistent.
3	2.61 - 3.40	Uncertain	Performance meets minimum expectations; acceptable but needs improvement.
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Performance is below expectations; inconsistently applied or ineffective practices.
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Performance is far below expectations; practices are poor or not evident.

Arbitrary Table 2C Students’ Academic Achievement

Scale	Mean Range	Rating Range	Interpretation	Description
5	4.21 - 5.00	91-100	Outstanding (O)	Students consistently exceed academic expectations; outstanding performance and active participation
4	3.41 – 4.20	86-90	Very Satisfactory (VS)	Students often meet or exceed expectations; good academic results and frequent participation.

3	2.61 - 3.40	81-85	Satisfactory (S)	Students meet basic expectations; performance and participation are average.
2	1.81 – 2.60	76-80	Fairly Satisfactory (FS)	Students often fall below expectations; limited academic success and engagement.
1	1.00 – 1.80	Below-75	Did not meet expectation (DM)	Students rarely meet expectations; poor academic performance and minimal participation.

Reliability and Validity

In assessing the study, researcher-developed questionnaires will be used. The questionnaire is composed of two types. Both questionnaires shall be subjected to validity and reliability tests.

Part I of the question is the demographic profile of the respondents which contains participant’s name and teaching strand they are handling. Part II is to test the level of effectiveness in administrative supervision in Julio Ledesma National High. This part consists of 15 items 3 areas: classroom observations, feedback and evaluation practices, instructional support. Part III question will determine level of teachers’ instructional performance in terms of classroom management, teaching strategies and assessment practices. Part IV questions will determine the level of students’ academic achievement in terms of academic performance. This will be responded using the 5-point of Likert scale responses in ascending order: 1-strongly disagree, 2-disagree, 3-uncertain, 4-agree and 5-strongly agree.

Data Collection Procedure

Before administering the questionnaire, permission will be sought from the superintendent and school administrators of the public secondary school to conduct the study among Grade 9,10 and 12 teachers. Upon approval, the participation of respondents will be entirely voluntary, and they will be notified regarding on the purpose of the study, nature, and scope.

During survey administration, the researcher personally administered the survey questionnaire. Respondents are expected to complete it within approximately one hour, using printed copies. Once the questionnaires are completed, the researcher handling the quantitative component will review them to ensure that all items have been answered.

After the administration, the quantitative data will be encoded into a tabulation format and analyzed statistically by a statistician.

Statistical Treatment

To analyze the data, both descriptive and inferential statistics are used. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation are applied to summarize and describe the levels of administrative supervision, teachers’ instructional performance and students’ academic achievement. To determine if there are meaningful relationships between the variables, Pearson’s Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient will be used. This test helped examine the strength and direction of the relationship between administrative supervision and teachers’ instructional performance and the relationship between administrative supervision and students’ academic achievement. A 0.05 level of significance is used to identify whether the results were statistically significant. All data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (version 27).

Ethical Considerations

To maintain the study's ethical soundness, during the conduct of this study the respondents’ rights, dignity, and privacy will be observed with respect to their protection. Before the data gathering starts, the researcher will ask formal approval from the school administrator and obtain the necessary research permit to conduct the study within the school.

Informed consent is necessary for the study to be conducted with mutual agreement between the researcher and the study participans. In this regard, the researcher will give them consent documents to sign, inquire about their readiness to join, and provide them with a justification of the purpose

and design of the study so they will understand why they must take part. Participants will be guaranteed the option to withdraw from the study if they feel uncomfortable.

The respondents' identities and whereabouts will remain confidential to protect their privacy. They could choose whether or not to include their names in the questionnaire, and their privacy was strongly valued. The questionnaire will be administered in a fair and non-threatening environment, ensuring that the teachers can respond honestly. Regarding confidentiality, all printed and soft data were appropriately maintained, preserved, and safeguarded in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. To guarantee the ethical soundness of these files, only the researcher, adviser, evaluators, and statistician will have access. All soft data must be deleted within the allotted time, and hard files must be manually disposed.

The procedures and conclusions that resulted in these production transparency decisions were provided by the researcher. The only objective of this study was to offer a reasonable explanation for the setting; no personal objectives were set. There was no conflict of interest, and the researchers were not paid for this work, even though they were affiliated with the Department of Education.

CHAPTER 3

RESULTS and DISCUSSIONS

This chapter presents the analysis, interpretation, and discussion of the research findings based on the responses of 99 teaching personnel from Julio Ledesma National High School, regarding administrative supervision and teachers' instructional performance. The data obtained through the research instrument were systematically processed and analyzed to address the study's specific problems.

Administrative Supervision

The influence of administrative supervision was probed in terms of classroom observation, feedback and evaluation practices and instructional support among the Grade 9,10 and 12 teachers at Julio Ledesma National High School.

Administrative Supervision in terms of Classroom observation

Table 3A. Administrative Supervision in terms of Classroom Observation

Classroom observation	SA	A	U	DA	SD	f	%	Sd	X-w	Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1	99	100			
Observation results are discussed with the teacher.	68	26	5	0	0	99	100	0.742	4.83	SA
Observation promotes professional growth.	61	38	0	0	0	99	100	0.822	4.65	SA
Administrators regularly observe classes.	60	37	2	0	0	99	100	0.818	4.64	SA
Observations are done using clear criteria.	84	13	2	0	0	99	100	0.816	4.61	SA
Observation schedules are communicated in advance.	64	35	0	0	0	99	100	0.828	4.59	SA

Total/General Mean	4.66	SA
N=99; \bar{X}_w = weighted mean; I= Interpretation; f=Frequency; %=Percentage; Sd=Standard Deviation		
Scale/Mean/Range/Interpretation: 5= 4.21-5.00 (Strongly Agree); 4= 3.41-4.20 (Agree); 3=2.61-3.40(Uncertain);2=1.81-2.60 (Disagree); 1=1.00-1.80 (Strongly Disagree)		

Table 3A presented the level of administrative supervision in terms of classroom observation. The results indicate that all indicators were rated *Strongly Agree*, suggesting that teachers perceive classroom observation as consistently and effectively practiced by school administrators.

Among the indicators, “Observation results are discussed with the teacher” acquired the highest mean score of 4.83, analyzed as *Strongly Agree*. This highlights the importance of post-observation conferences, where administrators provide feedback and engage teachers in meaningful discussions regarding their classroom performance. Such practice promotes clarity, reflection, and professional development among teachers.

The indicator “Observation promotes professional growth” followed with a mean of 4.65, indicating that teachers strongly believe classroom observations contribute positively to their continuous improvement and instructional competence. Similarly, “Administrators regularly observe classes” registered a mean of 4.64, reflecting the active involvement of school leaders in monitoring classroom instruction.

Moreover, “Observations are done using clear criteria” and “Observation schedules are communicated in advance” obtained mean scores of 4.62 and 4.59, respectively, both interpreted as *Strongly Agree*. These findings suggest that transparency, fairness, and proper planning are evident in the conduct of classroom observations, which help reduce teacher anxiety and build trust between administrators and teachers.

Overall, the findings implied that administrative supervision through classroom observation is effectively implemented and highly valued by teachers, contributing to improved instructional practices and a supportive school environment.

The very high ratings indicated that teachers feel observed systematically and that these observations are used constructively, which is a key practice in formative evaluation and professional growth (DepEd, 2017; CHED, 2015).

Table 3B. Administrative Supervision in terms of Feedback and Evaluation Practices

Feedback and Evaluation Practices	SA	A	U	DA	SD	f	%	Sd	\bar{X}_w	Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1	99	100			
Evaluation contributes to professional development.	64	34	1	0	0	99	100	0.827	4.94	SA
Feedback is constructive	68	31	0	0	0	99	100	0.836	4.69	SA
Feedback is given promptly after classroom observations.	54	44	1	0	0	99	100	0.909	4.64	SA
Teachers are evaluated fairly.	63	34	2	0	0	99	100	0.925	4.62	SA
Evaluation criteria are clearly explained to teachers.	94	4	1	0	0	99	100	0.988	4.54	SA

Total/General Mean	4.69	SA
N=99; X ^w = weighted mean; I= Interpretation; f=Frequency; %=Percentage; Sd=Standard Deviation		
Scale/Mean/Range/Interpretation: 5= 4.21-5.00 (Strongly Agree); 4= 3.41-4.20 (Agree); 3=2.61-3.40(Uncertain);2=1.81-2.60 (Disagree); 1=1.00-1.80 (Strongly Disagree)		

Table 3B presented the level of administrative supervision in terms of feedback and evaluation practices. The results showed that all indicators were rated *Strongly Agree*, indicating that teachers generally perceive the feedback and evaluation practices of school administrators as effective, fair, and supportive of their professional growth.

Among the indicators, “Evaluation contributes to professional development” received the highest mean score of 4.94, which was understood as *Strongly Agree*. This suggests that teachers strongly believe the evaluation process serves not merely as an appraisal mechanism but as a meaningful tool for enhancing their teaching competencies and overall professional development.

The indicator “Feedback is constructive” followed with a mean score of 4.69, reflecting teachers’ consensus that feedback issued by administrators is helpful, specific, and geared toward improvement. Likewise, “Feedback is given promptly after classroom observations” registered a mean of 4.64, highlighting the importance of timely feedback in reinforcing effective teaching practices and addressing areas for improvement while the observation experience is still fresh.

Furthermore, “Teachers are evaluated fairly” obtained a mean of 4.62, showing a high level of trust in the evaluation process objectivity and fairness. Meanwhile, “Evaluation criteria are clearly explained to teachers” garnered a mean of 4.54, interpreted as *Strongly Agree*, which suggests that transparency in evaluation standards is evident and contributes to teachers’ understanding and acceptance of the evaluation outcomes.

Overall, the findings imply that feedback and evaluation practices under administrative supervision are highly valued by teachers and are perceived as constructive, transparent, and development-oriented, thereby fostering a supportive environment for continuous instructional improvement.

Feedback and evaluation practices as part of administrative supervision are strongly supported by existing Department of Education policies. DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2015, which outlines the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS), emphasizes the use of clear evaluation criteria and the provision of timely and constructive feedback to improve teacher performance. Likewise, DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017, or the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), highlights that teacher evaluation is developmental and intended to support continuous professional growth. These policies emphasize stress fairness, transparency, and meaningful post-observation feedback as essential components of effective supervision. Consistent with these mandates, the empirical results of the present study revealed that teachers strongly agree that feedback is constructive, evaluations are fair, and the evaluation process contributes to their professional development.

Table 3C. Administrative Supervision in terms of Instructional Support

Instructional Support	SA	A	U	DA	SD	f	%	Sd	X ^w	Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1	99	100			
Administrators provide assistance with lesson planning.	96	3	0	0	0	99	100	0.994	4.97	SA
There is support for innovative teaching methods.	51	48	0	0	0	99	100	0.909	4.91	SA
Teachers feel supported	89	7	3	0	0	99	100	0.977	4.88	SA

in improving instruction.										
Professional development programs are offered regularly.	92	5	2	0	0	99	100	0.984	4.87	SA
Teachers have access to instructional materials.	90	6	3	0	0	99	100	0.979	4.51	SA
Total/General Mean									4.83	SA
N=99; \bar{X}_w = weighted mean; I= Interpretation; f=Frequency; %=Percentage; Sd=Standard Deviation										
Scale/Mean/Range/Interpretation: 5= 4.21-5.00 (Strongly Agree); 4= 3.41-4.20 (Agree); 3=2.61-3.40(Uncertain);2=1.81-2.60 (Disagree); 1=1.00-1.80 (Strongly Disagree)										

Table 3C showed that administrative supervision in terms of instructional support revealed that the indicator “Administrators provide assistance with lesson planning” obtained the highest rating, with a mean of 4.97, interpreted as *Strongly Agree*. These underscores show essential it is for school administrators to actively guide teachers in designing effective lessons, helping them feel more confident and prepared in the classroom. Next to it is the indicator “There is a support for innovative teaching methods.” This item received a weighted mean of 4.91, showing that teachers perceive encouragement from administrators to explore creative and engaging teaching strategies. Similarly, “Teachers feel supported in improving instruction” obtained a mean of 4.88, emphasizing that teachers experience motivation and practical support in enhancing their classroom practices. The indicator “Professional development programs are offered regularly” received a weighted mean of 4.87, reflecting the school’s commitment to continuous learning and skill enhancement for teachers. Lastly, “Teachers have access to instructional materials” gained a weighted mean of 4.52, indicating that most teachers agree that resources are provided to support effective teaching, although there may be slight room for improvement in accessibility.

Providing this kind of support allows teachers to enhance their teaching strategies, access necessary instructional materials, and try out innovative methods, all of which support professional growth and strengthen their learning. Teachers also strongly agreed that regular professional development programs are offered and that administrators support innovative teaching practices, indicating a supportive environment that encourages continuous improvement in teaching practices. Overall, the results suggest that instructional support under administrative supervision goes beyond procedures, creating an empowering atmosphere where teachers experience being valued, sustained, and driven to continuously improve their instruction.

These findings align with DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017 on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), which emphasizes that school leaders should provide guidance, resources, and opportunities for teachers’ professional development, and DepEd Order No. 35, s. 2016, which underscores collaborative learning and continuous professional growth through mechanisms such as the Learning Action Cell (LAC).

Table 4 Summary of Administrative Supervision

Indicators	Overall mean	Descriptive Rating
Instructional Support Iqa	4.83	Strongly Agree
Feedback and Evaluation Practices	4.69	Strongly Agree
Classroom Observation	4.66	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.73	Strongly Agree

Table 4 showed that all indicators of administrative supervision such as classroom observation, feedback and evaluation practices, and instructional support, received high mean ratings, with an overall weighted mean of 4.73 interpreted as Strongly Agree. This suggests that administrative

supervision in schools is perceived very positively by the respondents, indicating strong supervisory engagement and support in instructional processes and teacher evaluation.

These findings align with research showing that effective administrative and instructional supervision practices are essential for improving educational quality (Sugiar et al.,2025; Macalisang, 2023).

Teachers’ Instructional Performance

Teachers’ Instructional Performance was examined in terms of classroom management, teaching strategies, and assessment practices.

Instructional performance is a multifaceted construct that reflects teachers’ effectiveness in planning, delivering, and assessing their instruction. Research indicates that instructional practices such as the use of motivational strategies, varied teaching approaches, and assessment techniques which are strongly linked with teachers’ overall performance and quality of instruction, which in turn impact student learning outcomes (Bolante & San Gabriel, 2025; Bibon, 2022). Furthermore, engagement in professional development and instructional leadership practices significantly enhances teachers’ performance by strengthening pedagogical competencies (Alog & Oco, 2025; He, Guo & Abazie, 2024).

Table 5A. Teachers’ Instructional Performance in Terms of Classroom Management

Classroom Management	SA	A	U	DA	SD	f	%	Sd	X̄-w	Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1	99	100			
I address behavioral issues promptly.	72	26	1	0	0	99	100	0.948	4.78	SA
My class is organized, and time is used efficiently.	66	33	0	0	0	99	100	0.98	4.75	SA
I maintain discipline in the classroom.	52	44	3	0	0	99	100	0.906	4.72	SA
My classroom rules and routines are followed.	79	18	2	0	0	99	100	0.96	4.67	SA
The classroom environment is conducive to learning.	74	25	0	0	0	99	100	0.954	4.5	SA
Total/General Mean									4.68	SA
N=99; X̄-w= weighted mean; I= Interpretation; f=Frequency; %=Percentage; Sd=Standard Deviation										
Scale/Mean/Range/Interpretation: 5= 4.21-5.00 (Strongly Agree); 4= 3.41-4.20 (Agree); 3=2.61-3.40(Uncertain);2=1.81-2.60 (Disagree); 1=1.00-1.80 (Strongly Disagree)										

Table 5A showed that teachers’ instructional performance in terms of classroom management revealed that the indicator “The teacher addresses behavioral issues promptly” attained the highest weighted mean of 4.78, interpreted as *Strongly Agree*. This indicates that teachers are proactive in managing classroom behavior, ensuring that learning is not disrupted, and that students remain focused on their tasks. The indicator “The class is organized, and time is used efficiently” received a weighted mean of 4.75, highlighting the teacher’s ability to structure lessons effectively and make the most of instructional time. Similarly, “The teacher maintains discipline in the classroom” obtained a mean of 4.72, while “Classroom rules and routines are followed” had a mean of 4.67, both reflecting teachers’ consistent efforts to establish order and maintain a structured learning environment. Lastly, “The classroom environment is conducive to learning” received a weighted mean of 4.49, showing that teachers are generally successful in creating a positive and supportive atmosphere for their students.

These results are consistent with DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017, which emphasizes that effective classroom management is a core standard under the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), requiring teachers to maintain discipline, organize learning spaces, and manage time efficiently to facilitate student learning. Likewise, DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015, through the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS), underscores that teachers' classroom management skills should be observed, evaluated, and continuously improved to enhance teaching effectiveness. Overall, the findings suggest that teachers demonstrate strong classroom management skills, which are essential for creating an organized, disciplined, and productive learning environment for students.

Table 5B. Teachers' Instructional Performance in terms of Teaching Strategies

Teaching Strategies	SA	A	U	DA	SD	f	%	Sd	X ^w	Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1	99	100			
My instruction is aligned with learning objectives.	64	34	1	0	0	99	100	0.838	4.94	SA
My lessons cater to different learning styles.	68	31	0	0	0	99	100	0.942	4.69	SA
I use a variety of teaching methods.	54	44	1	0	0	99	100	0.911	4.64	SA
I provided engaging lessons	63	34	2	0	0	99	100	0.922	4.62	SA
I used technology effectively in instruction.	94	4	1	0	0	99	100	0.988	4.94	SA
Total/General Mean									4.69	SA
N=99; X ^w = weighted mean; I= Interpretation; f=Frequency; %=Percentage; Sd=Standard Deviation										
Scale/Mean/Range/Interpretation: 5= 4.21-5.00 (Strongly Agree); 4= 3.41-4.20 (Agree); 3=2.61-3.40(Uncertain);2=1.81-2.60 (Disagree); 1=1.00-1.80 (Strongly Disagree)										

Table 4B showed that teachers' instructional performance in terms of teaching strategies revealed that the indicator "My instruction is aligned with learning objectives" obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.94, interpreted as *Strongly Agree*. This finding highlights that teachers plan and deliver lessons that are clearly focused on achieving specific learning goals, ensuring that students gain the intended knowledge and skills. The indicator "My lessons cater to different learning styles" received a weighted mean of 4.69, showing that teachers design instruction to address the diverse needs of learners, thus promoting inclusivity and engagement. Similarly, "I use a variety of teaching methods" obtained a mean of 4.64, and "I provided engaging lessons" had a mean of 4.62, reflecting teachers' commitment to using varied and interactive strategies to sustain student interest. Lastly, "I used technology effectively in instruction" received a weighted mean of 4.54, indicating that teachers integrate digital tools to enhance learning, although there may still be opportunities to expand their use in the future.

These findings are supported by DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017, which emphasizes the use of varied teaching strategies and alignment of instruction with learning competencies as key standards under the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). Additionally, DepEd Order No. 8, s.

2015, through the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS), highlights the importance of planning and implementing instructional strategies that address learners' needs and promote effective learning outcomes.

Overall, the results suggest that teachers employ diverse, engaging, and learner-centered teaching strategies that are aligned with curricular objectives, contributing to high-quality instruction and learning.

Table 5C. Teachers' Instructional Performance in terms Assessment Practices

Assessment Practices	SA	A	U	DA	SD	f	%	Sd	X ^w	Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1	99	100			
Feedback is provided on student performance.	85	14	0	0	0	99	100	0.974	4.94	SA
My students are informed of grading criteria	52	47	0	0	0	99	100	0.91	4.9	SA
I use varied assessment tools.	89	10	0	0	0	99	100	0.982	4.86	SA
Assessment results guide future instruction.	93	6	0	0	0	99	100	0.989	4.85	SA
My assessment tasks reflect the learning objectives	84	15	0	0	0	99	100	0.972	4.53	SA
Total/General Mean									4.82	SA
N=99; X ^w = weighted mean; I= Interpretation; f=Frequency; %=Percentage; Sd=Standard Deviation										
Scale/Mean/Range/Interpretation: 5= 4.21-5.00 (Strongly Agree); 4= 3.41-4.20 (Agree); 3=2.61-3.40(Uncertain);2=1.81-2.60 (Disagree); 1=1.00-1.80 (Strongly Disagree)										

Table 5C showed that teachers' instructional performance in terms of assessment practices revealed that the indicator "Feedback is provided on student performance" obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.94, interpreted as *Strongly Agree*. This indicates that teachers consistently provide timely and meaningful feedback, helping students understand their strengths and areas for improvement in their writing. The indicator "My students are informed of grading criteria" received a weighted mean of 4.90, highlighting the transparency and fairness of the assessment process in the course. Similarly, "I use varied assessment tools" obtained a mean of 4.86, and "Assessment results guide future instruction" had a mean of 4.85, reflecting teachers' efforts to use diverse assessment strategies to inform teaching and ensure learning objectives are met. Lastly, "My assessment tasks reflect the learning objectives" received a mean of 4.53, showing that assessments are generally aligned with lesson goals, though there is slight room to strengthen alignment across all tasks.

These findings are consistent with DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017, which emphasizes the use of valid, varied, and competency-aligned assessment practices under the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). Likewise, DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015, through the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS), highlights that assessment should provide actionable feedback and guide instructional decisions.

Overall, the results suggest that teachers implement systematic, transparent, and learner-centered assessment practices that support student learning, inform instruction, and enhance teaching effectiveness.

Table 6 Summary of Table of Teachers' Instructional Performance

Indicators	Overall mean	Descriptive Rating
Assessment Practices	4.482	Strongly Agree
Teaching Practices	4.69	Strongly Agree
Classroom Management	4.68	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.73	Strongly Agree

Table 6 showed that all indicators of teachers' instructional performance in terms of classroom management, teaching practices, and assessment practices got high mean scores, with an overall weighted mean of 4.73 which is interpreted as Strongly Agree. This concluded that teachers are perceived to perform effectively in managing classrooms, delivering instructional and learning content as well as conducting students' assessment.

The results showed that a consistent high rating across indicators which suggest strong instructional competence and professional practice among the teachers. Studies showed that strong instructional practices and ongoing assessments enhance and support students' learning and reflect teacher quality (Darling-Hammond, 2021; Santiago & Bernando, 2024)

Table 7. Level of Students' Academic Achievement

Level	5 (91-100)		4(86-90)		3(81-85)		2 (76-80)		1 (below-75)		Total	Sd	w \bar{x}	I	
	Outstanding		Very Satisfactory		Satisfactory		Fairly Satisfactory		Did not Meet Expectation						
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%					
Gr. 12	209	22.2	182	19	431	46	115	12.22	5	0.53	942	100	1.351	3.5	VS
Gr.10	68	11.7	86	15	314	54	86	14.83	26	4.48	580	100	1.096	3.14	S
Gr. 9	73	13	119	21	208	37	124	22.06	38	6.76	562	100	1.102	3.12	S
Total/General Weighted Mean	350	16.8	387	19	953	46	325	15.6	69	3.31	2084	100		3.3	S
N=350; X \bar{w} = Weighted Mean; I= Interpretation; f= Frequency; %= Percentage; Sd= Standard Deviation															
Scale/Mean Range/Interpretation: 5=91-100 (Outstanding); 4=86-90 (Very Satisfactory);3=81-85 (Satisfactory);2= 79-80 (Fairly Satisfactory);1= below-74 (Did not Meet Expectation)															

Table 7 showed the overall weighted mean for the students' academic performance across Grade 9, Grade 10, and Grade 12 was **3.30**, interpreted as *Satisfactory*. This showed that, students are achieving outcomes at a level that meets expectations, demonstrating adequate understanding of the subjects, although there remains room for improvement to achieve higher levels of proficiency.

When looking at the distribution of grades, many students fell within the *Satisfactory* range of 81–85, representing 45.73% of the total respondents. This was followed by students who achieved *Very Satisfactory* (86–90), comprising 18.57%, and those with *Outstanding* grades (91–100), representing 16.79% of the total. Meanwhile, a smaller portion of students earned *Fairly Satisfactory* (76–80) at 15.60%, and a few students fell into the *Did Not Meet Expectation* category (below 75), accounting for only 3.31%. These findings suggest that most students are performing satisfactorily, with a significant portion showing potential to reach higher achievement levels with additional support and guidance.

This performance profile has implications for both instruction and administrative supervision, as it highlights the need for teachers to use differentiated and learner-centered strategies to help more students progress toward higher achievement levels. The DepEd grading and assessment policies emphasize that assessment should be used to inform instruction and provide meaningful feedback that guides both teaching and learning. According to DepEd's assessment and grading guidelines (e.g., DepEd Order 31 on assessment and grading).

Table 8. Relationship Between Administrative Supervision and Teachers' Instructional Performance

Variables	<i>r</i>	Interpretation	<i>p</i> value	Decision	Remark
Administrative Supervision and Teachers' Instructional Performance	.999	Very high correlation	.000	Reject H_0	Significant

Note. $N = 99$. Level of significance set at $\alpha = .05$.

Table 8 presented the relationship between administrative supervision and teachers' instructional performance. Pearson's product-moment correlation was used to determine the degree of relationship between the variables. The result showed a correlation coefficient of $r = .999$, indicating a very high positive correlation between administrative supervision and teachers' instructional performance.

The data indicated a statistically significant relationship between administrative supervision and teachers' instructional performance. This finding is supported by the obtained p value of .000, which is less than the set level of significance ($p < .05$). Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This result suggests that administrative supervision is significantly associated with teachers' instructional performance.

This finding is consistent with DepEd policies, which emphasize the importance of effective instructional supervision in improving teaching quality. According to DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017, school leaders are expected to provide ongoing guidance, feedback, and support to teachers to ensure that instruction meets the standards of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST).

Additionally, DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2015 through the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) underscores the link between structured administrative supervision and improved teacher performance outcomes. Research also supports this relationship, suggesting that regular classroom observation, feedback, and instructional support are positively associated with teacher effectiveness and student learning (Reños & Pontillas, 2024).

Table 9. Relationship Between Administrative Supervision and Students' Academic Achievement

Variables	<i>r</i>	Interpretation	<i>P</i> value	Decision	Remark
Administrative Supervision and Students' Academic Achievement	.116	Very low correlation	.863	Accept H_0	Not significant

Note. $N = 99$. Level of significance set at $\alpha = .05$.

Table 9 showed the relationship between administrative supervision and students' academic achievement. Pearson's product-moment correlation analysis yielded a correlation coefficient of $r = .116$, indicating a very low positive correlation between the two variables.

Although the correlation between administrative supervision and students' academic achievement is weak and positive, the relationship is not statistically significant. The computed p value of .863 is greater than the level of significance ($p > .05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This finding indicates that administrative supervision does not have a significant relationship with students' academic achievement in this study.

The data revealed very high levels in both administrative supervision and teachers' instructional performance. Although inferential statistics (e.g., correlation or regression) were not conducted within the provided data, the consistency of high means suggests a positive relationship.

This finding highlighted that students' achievement is influenced by multiple factors beyond administrative supervision, including teaching strategies, learning resources, learner motivation, and socio-economic conditions. Nevertheless, DepEd policies, such as DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017 (PPST) and DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2015 (RPMS), still emphasize that effective supervision is

essential for enhancing instructional practices, which indirectly supports student learning outcomes over time. Supporting literature also notes that while administrative guidance improves teaching quality, the effect on student achievement may require sustained implementation, additional support mechanisms, and alignment with learner-centered strategies (Reños & Pontillas, 2024).

CHAPTER IV

Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendation

Summary of Findings

This section presented the major findings of the study based on the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered. The reported outcomes were arranged according to the research questions and objectives of the study.

The findings indicated very high levels of administrative supervision across three dimensions: classroom observation, feedback and evaluation practices, and instructional support. In classroom observation, teachers strongly agreed that observations are conducted systematically and contribute to professional growth, with “Observation results are discussed with the teacher” receiving the highest mean of 4.83. Feedback and evaluation practices were also rated highly, with “Evaluation contributes to professional development” obtaining a mean of 4.94, reflecting the perceived fairness, transparency, and constructive nature of administrative feedback. Instructional support likewise received strong ratings, particularly for “Administrators provide assistance with lesson planning” (mean = 4.97) and “Support for innovative teaching methods” (mean = 4.91), highlighting the school’s commitment to fostering teacher growth and instructional quality. These findings align with DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017 (PPST) and DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2015 (RPMS), which emphasize ongoing instructional supervision, professional development, and meaningful feedback as essential for teacher effectiveness.

Teachers’ instructional performance was also rated highly across classroom management, teaching strategies, and assessment practices. The highest-rated indicators included “The teacher addresses behavioral issues promptly” (mean = 4.78), “My instruction is aligned with learning objectives” (mean = 4.94), and “Feedback is provided on student performance” (mean = 4.94). These results indicate that teachers effectively manage classrooms, employ varied and learner-centered teaching strategies, and implement systematic, competency-aligned assessment practices to support student learning. DepEd policies reinforce these standards, particularly through the PPST and RPMS, which guide teaching performance and continuous professional improvement

The overall **students’ academic performance** had a weighted mean of 3.30, interpreted as *Satisfactory*, with most learners achieving grades in the 81–85 range. While most students met the expected competency level, the findings suggest that differentiated instruction, targeted interventions, and additional support are necessary to help more learners attain higher achievement levels.

There is a very strong and significant relationship between administrative supervision and teachers’ instructional performance. This suggests that effective supervision provided by school administrators plays an important role in enhancing how teachers perform their instructional duties. When administrators regularly guide, support, and monitor teachers, it positively influences their classroom practices and overall teaching effectiveness. The statistical results further confirm that this relationship is significant, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. These findings highlight the vital role of school administrators in promoting professional growth among teachers and in creating a supportive school environment that contributes to improved teaching and learning outcomes.

This finding indicates that administrative supervision does not have a significant relationship with students’ academic achievement in this study. This suggests that effective supervisory practices play a crucial role in enhancing teachers’ ability to deliver quality instruction. Through guidance, feedback, and professional support, administrative supervision contributes to improved instructional

practices in the classroom. On the other hand, the findings reveal that administrative supervision does not have a significant relationship with students' academic achievement. While a slight positive association was observed, it was not statistically significant, indicating that students' academic performance is influenced by various factors beyond administrative supervision. Overall, the results suggest that administrative supervision supports student learning indirectly by strengthening teachers' instructional performance rather than directly affecting academic achievement.

Conclusions

The study concluded that administrative supervision at Julio Ledesma National High School is highly effective, as evidenced by very high ratings across classroom observation, feedback and evaluation practices, and instructional support. Teachers strongly agreed that supervision is systematic, constructive, and promotes professional growth. Teachers' instructional performance is high, especially in managing classrooms, using teaching strategies, and giving assessments. Top indicators include addressing behavioral issues promptly, aligning instruction with learning objectives, and providing feedback on student performance.

Students' overall academic performance is satisfactory, with most scoring 81–85. While students meet expected standards, extra support and different teaching strategies are needed to help more students reach higher grades.

There is a very strong positive relationship between supervision and teacher performance ($r = .999$, $p = .000$). This means that guidance, feedback, and support from administrators greatly improve how teachers teach. However, administrative supervision has little direct effect on student grades. While supervision improves teaching quality, student achievement depends on other factors like teaching methods, resources, motivation, and support. In relation to the following results, this concluded that there might be another underlying factor that would contribute or affects the students' academic performance.

Recommendations

Considering the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. **School administrators** should sustain and further strengthen effective supervisory practices, particularly regular classroom observations, constructive feedback, and fair evaluation, to continuously enhance teachers' instructional performance.
2. **Teachers** should actively engage in professional development activities and utilize supervisory feedback to further improve instructional strategies and assessment practices.
3. **Educational planners** and policymakers may use the findings of this study as a foundation for strengthening administrative supervision guidelines and schemes aimed at improving teaching quality and student academic achievement. School administrators should enhance supervisory strategies that support teachers' professional development. Teachers are encouraged to utilize supervisory feedback for instructional improvement. Future researchers may explore additional factors influencing instructional performance.
4. **Future Researchers** future studies may explore other factors affecting student achievement beyond administrative supervision, such as teaching strategies, learner motivation, and socio-economic conditions. They may also examine the long-term impact of administrative supervision on teacher performance and student learning or replicate the study in other schools for comparison.

FACULTY DEVELOPMENT ACTION PLAN

Based on the Study: *Influence of Administrative Supervision on Teacher's Instructional Performance and Students' academic Achievement*

Locale: Julio Ledesma National High School Target Groups: All JHS and SHS teachers at Julio Ledesma National High School

Focus: Enhancing Teachers’ Instructional Performance through Effective Administrative Supervision

General Objective

To determine the influence of administrative supervision on teachers’ instructional performance and students’ academic achievement at Julio Ledesma National High School and to enhance teaching effectiveness through effective supervision aligned with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST).

Specific Objectives

1. To improve classroom observation and feedback practices.
2. To promote learner-centered and innovative teaching methods.

Table.1 PPST Level Target: Proficient – Highly Proficient

Focus Area	PPST Domain / Level	Objectives	Activities / Strategies	Persons Responsible	Timeline	KSA Success Indicators	Budget (₱)	Source of Funds
Instructional Leadership & Supervision	Domain 7: Personal Growth & Professional Engagement (Highly Proficient)	Strengthen instructional supervision and leadership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular classroom observations with post-observation conferencing • Coaching & mentoring programs 	School Head, Master Teachers, Department Heads	Whole School Year	<p>Knowledge: Understand effective supervision and feedback practices.</p> <p>Skill: Conducts Structured observations and coaching sessions.</p> <p>Attitude: Demonstrate commitment to instructional improvement</p>	10,000	School MOOE / INSET Fund
Classroom Management	Domain 2: Learning Environment (Proficient)	Enhance classroom organization and behavior management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INSET on positive discipline & classroom routines • Peer observation & best practice sharing 	Teachers, Master Teachers	Quarterly	<p>Knowledge: Comprehend positive discipline and classroom management strategies.</p> <p>Skill: Maintains organized and learner-centered classroom routines.</p> <p>Attitude: Shows fairness, consistency, and patience.</p>	5,000	School MOOE / LAC Fund
Teaching Strategies	Domain 3: Diversity of Learners & Domain 4: Curriculum & Planning (Proficient)	Promote learner-centered and innovative teaching strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LAC sessions on active learning & differentiated instruction • Demonstration lessons & lesson study 	Teachers, LAC Leaders	Monthly	<p>Skill: Increased use of varied instructional strategies; teacher reflections</p>	8,000	School MOOE / LAC Fund
Assessment Practices	Domain 5: Assessment & Reporting (Proficient)	Strengthen formative and summative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop on rubric development, assessment for 	Teachers, Subject Heads	Quarterly	<p>Knowledge: Understands the importance of alignment</p>	5,000	School MOOE / LAC Fund

		assessment skills	learning, and feedback			of assessment tools with learning objectives; timely feedback Attitude: Displays creativity and flexibility in instruction.		
Technology Integration	Domain 4: Curriculum & Planning & Domain 7: Professional Growth (Proficient)	Enhance ICT-supported instruction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training on DepEd digital platforms and ICT tools • Development of technology-integrated lesson plans 	ICT Coordinator, Teachers	Quarterly	Skills: Increased the use of ICT and integrate in instruction; submission of tech-based lesson plans	12,000	DepEd Tech Grant / School MOOE
Professional Growth & Research	Domain 7: Personal Growth & Professional Engagement (Highly Proficient)	Promote continuous professional development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in webinars, seminars, graduate studies • Conduct action research or innovation projects 	Teachers, School Head	Whole School Year	Knowledge: Understands current educational trends and research practices. Skills: Engages in CPD and conducts action research. Attitude: Demonstrates lifelong learning and professional responsibility.		

Total Budget: ₱55,000

Monitoring & Evaluation

1. Classroom observation and RPMS/IPCRF scores
2. LAC documentation and teacher reflections
3. Lesson study reports and action research outputs
4. Student academic performance trends

Notes

1. Activities are aligned to PPST Proficient–Highly Proficient levels.
2. Supports DepEd frameworks: LAC, INSET, RPMS/IPCRF, SBM.
3. Funding sources: School MOOE, LAC fund, DepEd tech grants, CPD grants.

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